

Polarity Disposition Or Distribution

The measure or appraisal of experience influences the degree of detail that is discerned in what we encounter. Experience here denotes any event or definition we come across. Any object that we can perceive whether it is a doorknob, or a specific feeling or thought is an experience for the purposes of this brief discussion. Perception occurs within a background of measure and there is a possibility that the rarefication of this background might alter perceptual acuity. Appraisal or measure might be viewed as a constitutive phenomena, one that determines delimitation of any fashion. The perception of any experience occurs within a range or continuum of measure and the distribution of the objects of experience could be viewed as a matter of the tendency to polarize. How we perceive a doorknob or a difficult feeling is a function of the range of measure that we have access to. It is this range of measure that is primary. The perception of experience as well as the objects of experience arise within this range of measure and the disposition to polarize creates the delimitation into structure of any kind. The structure of a thought or feeling is thus essentially a form of polarization as is their perception.

Reference:

Ghosh, Swarajit. (2022). A Theory of Adaptive Processing: From Confinement to Maneuverability. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6979245>